

Comparative Analysis of Yarns Spun from Textile Waste

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Abstract:

The rapid growth of the textile and apparel sector has led to a substantial increase in pre-consumer textile cutting waste, highlighting the need for efficient recycling strategies to promote sustainable material utilisation. In the present study, mixed textile cutting waste generated during garment manufacturing was mechanically recycled and blended with virgin viscose fibres to enhance fibre processability. Recycled fibres were converted into slivers through carding and subsequently spun into yarns using both ring and rotor spinning systems. Produced yarns were evaluated in terms of linear density, tensile strength, and elongation behaviour. Woven fabrics were further prepared using recycled yarns in the weft direction with cotton warp yarns, and their structural properties, such as thickness and fabric density, were analysed.

Results indicated that recycled fibre slivers showed hank values close to those of virgin viscose slivers, suggesting satisfactory blending compatibility. Ring-spun yarns obtained from recycled fibres exhibited coarse structure with higher extensibility but comparatively lower tenacity. In contrast, the rotor-spun yarns—integrated with a 25% virgin viscose blend—achieved a significantly finer linear density and superior tensile performance, as the added viscose fibers facilitated better fiber consolidation and stress distribution within the yarn structure. Fabric evaluation revealed that rotor-spun yarns produced comparatively thinner and more compact fabrics, whereas ring-spun recycled yarns generated bulkier fabric structures. Furthermore, fabrics woven with sateen weave demonstrated higher warp density compared to plain weave due to the presence of longer yarn floats and fewer interlacements. Findings confirm that mechanically recycled mixed textile cutting waste can be effectively transformed into functional yarns and woven fabrics, demonstrating the potential of such recycling strategies for sustainable textile manufacturing.

Keywords: Mechanical recycling, Pre-consumer garment waste, Recycled yarn production, Ring and rotor spinning, Sustainable woven fabrics, Textile waste recycling

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1. Introduction

The textile industry is one of the largest generators of solid waste, with a significant proportion arising from pre-consumer cutting waste produced during garment manufacturing. This type of waste, although relatively clean and uniform compared to post-consumer textiles, is often underutilised and disposed of through landfilling or incineration, leading to environmental and economic concerns. In the context of increasing emphasis on circular economy and sustainable material utilisation, mechanical recycling of textile cutting waste into value-added yarns and fabrics has gained considerable attention [1].

Mechanical recycling offers an attractive route for textile waste valorisation due to its low chemical and energy requirements. However, fibres recovered through mechanical processes typically suffer from reduced length, higher irregularity, and poor cohesion, which adversely affect spinnability and final product performance [2]. To overcome these limitations, blending recycled fibres with virgin fibres has been widely explored as a practical approach to enhance fibre processability and yarn quality. Among various virgin fibres, viscose is particularly suitable due to its cellulosic nature, good fibre uniformity, and compatibility with recycled textile fibres [3].

Spinning technology also plays a critical role in determining the performance of recycled yarns. Conventional ring spinning provides good yarn strength and extensibility, but is sensitive to fibre quality, while rotor spinning is more tolerant of shorter and heterogeneous fibres, making it suitable for recycled fibre processing. A comparative evaluation of these spinning systems is therefore essential to understand their suitability for recycled fibre-based yarn production [4]. Furthermore, the translation of recycled yarn characteristics into fabric properties depends not only on yarn structure but also on fabric construction parameters, such as weave type and yarn float length [2].

In this study, mixed textile cutting waste containing different textile fabrics and their blends was mechanically recycled and blended with virgin viscose fibres to improve fibre processability. Recycled fibre slivers were spun using both ring and rotor spinning systems, and the resulting yarns were characterised for their linear density and tensile properties. The yarns were subsequently woven into fabrics using plain and satin weave structures to evaluate the influence of yarn type and floated yarn length on fabric thickness and structural parameters. The study aims to assess the feasibility of converting mixed textile cutting waste without segregation into usable yarns and fabrics and to identify suitable spinning and fabric construction routes for recycled textile materials.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Mixed textile cutting waste was collected from garment industries and tailor shops. This cutting waste was not segregated according to the type of material, but it was used as it is, irrespective of material type, i.e., cotton, polyester, viscose, etc. The pre-consumer mixed textile waste was selected due to its minimal contamination and suitability for mechanical recycling. Virgin viscose fibres were obtained from Birla Cellulose Ltd., Kosamba, and were used to improve fibre processability and yarn formation.

2.2 Mechanical Recycling and Fibre Preparation

The collected cutting waste was manually cut into small pieces and processed on a miniature flat carding machine to open, clean, and convert the fabric waste into fibrous form. The prepared carded web was further processed through a second carding stage using a trumpet (10 mm bore size) to produce slivers of approximately 0.21 hank. To enhance the structural integrity and eventual durability of the fabric, 25 wt% virgin viscose fibres were incorporated during the second carding passage; this addition stabilized the recycled fibre matrix and ensured more uniform fibre distribution throughout the yarn.

2.3 Yarn Spinning

The recycled fibre slivers were spun using both ring and rotor spinning systems to evaluate their processability. For ring spinning, the sliver was directly processed on a miniature ring frame to produce yarns through the drafting and twisting processes and was labelled as Y1, i.e., Ring-spun yarn from mixed waste (Figure 1a).

Figure 1 - Prepared Yarn Samples a) Rotot-Spun Yarn b) Ring-Spun Yarn

For rotor spinning, two slivers were fed simultaneously: one recycled fibre sliver (0.21 hank) and one virgin viscose fibre sliver (0.18 hank). The rotor speed was maintained at 30,000 rpm, and the opening roller speed was set at 8,000 rpm. The produced yarn was subsequently wound onto a package and labelled as Y2, i.e., Rotor-spun yarn with viscose + mixed waste (Figure 1b).

2.4 Fabric Formation

Woven fabric samples were produced on a handloom using the recycled yarns as weft and 100% cotton yarns as warp. Four fabric samples were prepared based on the spinning method and weave type, i.e., plain and satin fabrics woven with ring-spun and rotor-spun recycled yarns. Photographs of prepared samples are shown in Figure 2, and their coding was used as follows:

- Y1 in weft, plain weave
- Y2 in weft, plain weave
- Y1 in weft, satin weave
- Y2 in weft, satin weave

Figure 2 - Samples Prepared on A Handloom, a) Y1 In Weft, Plain Weave, b) Y2 In Weft, Plain Weave, c) Y1 In Weft, Satin Weave, d) Y2 In Weft, Satin Weave

3. Results and Discussion

The increasing demand for sustainable textile materials has accelerated interest in recycled fibres as alternatives to virgin fibres. In this study, the processability and performance of non-segregated mechanically recycled fibres were evaluated through sliver hank, yarn properties (denier, strength, elongation, tenacity), and fabric characteristics (thickness, EPI, and PPI).

3.1 Sliver Hank

The sliver hank obtained from virgin viscose fibres was 0.18, while the sliver produced from recycled fibres derived from mixed textile waste exhibited a slightly higher hank value of 0.21. This could be due to non-segregation of fibres, which consist of fibres of varying densities, which may have led to a change in hank value. The close similarity between these sliver hank values (0.18 for viscose and 0.21 for recycled) confirms excellent compatibility during blending, which is essential for ensuring the long-term structural integrity and

durability of the resulting fabric. This compatibility allowed the recycled fiber sliver to be processed seamlessly on standard machinery, facilitating a stable spinning process that directly contributes to the consistency of the final textile product.

3.2 Yarn Denier and Tensile Properties

The denier and tensile properties of the produced yarns are summarised in Table 1. It can be seen that the ring-spun recycled yarn (Y1) exhibited a very high denier (9000), which can be attributed to the use of carded sliver as an input and the limited drafting capability of the miniature ring frame used in this study[5]. As a result, the yarn structure remained coarse and bulky. Apart from this, Y1 showed a high maximum load-bearing capacity; however, its tenacity was relatively low due to its coarse structure. This may be due to poor fibre alignment and a higher proportion of short and recycled fibres[6]. Analysis also showed that ring-spun yarn has relatively high extension, which may be attributed to the nature of ring-spun yarn having a good twisted configuration, which allows fibre migration, leading to high stretch[7].

Table 1 - Yarn Properties

Type of Yarn	Denier	Max Load (gf)	Elongation (%)	Tenacity (gpd)
Ring-spun Recycled only (Y1)	9000	2135.41	19.76	0.24
Rotor: Viscose + Recycled (Y2)	945	561.61	9.11	0.59

In contrast, the rotor-spun yarn blended with viscose and recycled fibres (Y2) displayed a significantly lower denier (945) along with improved tensile properties. The higher tenacity of Y2 indicates better fibre consolidation and stress distribution within the yarn structure. These characteristics make rotor-spun blended yarns more suitable for short staple fibres, particularly where uniformity and strength are required.

3.3 Fabric Properties

Fabric samples woven using different recycled yarns in the weft direction were analysed for thickness, ends per inch (EPI), and picks per inch (PPI), and the results are presented in Table 2. Fabrics produced with ring-spun recycled yarn (Y1) exhibited substantially higher thickness values in both plain and sateen weaves. This increase in thickness is primarily attributed to the coarser ring-spun recycled yarn. Conversely, fabrics woven with rotor-spun viscose-recycled yarn (Y2) showed lower thickness due to the finer yarn count and improved fibre packing.

Table 2 - Fabric Properties

Weft Yarn Type	Weave	Thickness (mm)	EPI	PPI
Y2 (Rotor Viscose Mix)	Sateen	0.852	46	22
Y1 (Ring Recycled)	Sateen	1.833	50	10
Y2 (Rotor Viscose Mix)	Plain	0.841	40	16
Y1 (Ring Recycled)	Plain	2.061	40	10

It can also be observed that fabric woven with sateen weave showed higher EPI values compared to plain weave. This can be due to the longer weft floats with sateen weave, which allows greater weft thread shrinkage due to reduced interlacement points, that groups more warp threads per unit length [8]. Also, EPI values were relatively higher for ring-spun yarn than rotor-spun yarn in sateen weave-based woven fabric[6]. This may be due to less PPI, which results in higher shrinkage of warp threads per unit length [8, 9]. This behaviour was not observed with plain weave, where frequent interlacements limit yarn mobility and negate the influence of yarn structure on warp density [8, 9]. Apart from this, variations in PPI were mainly influenced by irregular beat-up force on the handloom and different yarn count.

4. Conclusion

This study investigated the mechanical recycling of mixed textile cutting waste and its subsequent processing into yarns and woven fabrics without segregating it as per type of material. The incorporation of virgin viscose fibres during carding enabled stable sliver formation and improved processability of recycled fibres without major machine adjustments. Comparative spinning trials demonstrated that rotor spinning was more effective than ring spinning for producing finer and stronger yarns from recycled fibre blends, whereas ring-spun recycled yarns exhibited higher bulk and elongation but lower tenacity.

Fabric analysis showed that yarn structure and spinning method significantly influenced fabric thickness and density, with rotor-spun viscose-recycled yarns yielding thinner and more compact fabrics. Additionally, weave structure played an important role in determining fabric parameters, as sateen weave fabrics exhibited higher warp density than plain weave due to increased yarn float length and reduced interlacements. The results confirm that mixed textile cutting waste can be successfully recycled into functional yarns and fabrics using appropriate blending, spinning, and fabric construction strategies, thereby supporting sustainable material utilisation in textile manufacturing.

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